

Scientific Interpretation of the Case Semantic Category in Linguistics

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Abstract:

The semantic category "condition" is one of the vast and intricate subjects in linguistics. This area of study examines the various ways in which a person's physical, emotional, and social states are expressed through language. State semantic category: a semantic category that describes an object's or person's current state.

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In the field of linguistics, the semantic category "condition" is one of the broad and complex topics. This category studies the ways in which language is used to express different physical, mental and social conditions of a person. State semantic category is a semantic category that provides information about the state of people and objects.

It is known that the problem of studying the mental state of a person is one of the urgent problems of psychology. This issue is covered in detail in the educational literature of this field. And linguists are interested in the issue of the expression of human mental state in language.

The case semantic category studies the meaning of words and expressions and their ability to express the states of various objects depending on their use. Through this category, it is possible to analyze how languages reflect changes in the natural and social environment, and how to express the state of objects. For example, English has many state adjectives ("happy", "sad", "broken", "smooth") that describe different objects and their properties. The scientific interpretation of the status semantic category helps to expand the semantic possibilities of the language, to analyze its expressive resources, and to understand what functions the language can perform in different cultural contexts. Through this category, linguists conduct comparative studies that reveal the commonalities and differences between languages.

In all languages, the recurrent case semantic category is represented by various units in the language. In many languages, predicates expressing state are distinguished.

Psychology of states. Reader / Ed. A. O. Prokhorova. – M., 2004; Workshop on the psychology of states: Textbook / Ed. prof. A. O. Prokhorova. – M., 2004; Shcherbatykh Yu. V., Mosina A. N. Differentiation of mental states and other psychological phenomena. – Kazan, 2008. – P. 526-528.

According to I.N. Yakovleva, the semantic category of situation appears in the structure of a sentence at the predicative level in the language and has a hidden grammatical character. The semantic category of case is formed due to the grammatical connection of the predicate with a certain type of subject, as well as the forms of the verb in the relations of valence, tense, type, word-forming forms, and adverbial determinants.

For a long time, the problem of the semantic category of case has been one of the central issues of linguistic semantics. The problem of the speech expression of the semantic category of status is the object of study of various linguistic studies even now.

A state category basically represents the type or condition of a person or object at a particular time or period. This concept covers various factors such as a person's lifestyle, mood, health or the physical condition of an object. The issue of the representation of the semantic category of state in all level units of the language has not yet been studied in many languages. Its study plays an important role in understanding the meaning and structure of language, as well as ways of self-expression of a person. Through this category, scientists strive to reveal the universal and cultural characteristics of language and to gain a deeper understanding of the role of language in human life.

The definition of the word "state" is given in several dictionaries, in particular, in the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, it is explained as follows: "1. The existing situation. 2. Physical or mental expression, appearance; appearance, voice. 3. Strength, medicine, skill; power" .

This word is mentioned in the encyclopedia of Russian sociology: "1. Features of any system that reflect the location of the environment relative to the coordinate objects. 2. Physical well-being, mood. 3. Social position, title. 4. "Property, property" is commented.

Several theoretical views can be given regarding the analysis of the semantics of the status category and the study of its reflection in the language. "Cognitive Maps Theory" developed by Talmy Hizbrun is an example of this, "language is represented in the brain through mental models or "maps". State semantics help describe the states of objects in these models and their changes. For example, in the English sentence "The vase is on the table", the location of the vase is reflected in a clear mental map. This theory offers important approaches in linguistics to analyze the semantics of the category of case and to generate concepts related to its specific foundations in language.

"Prototype Theory", according to Eleanor Roche, "semantic categories of situations sometimes do not have clear boundaries, but rather are understood as clouds of meaning around them." For example, the quality "happy" includes a number of different but similar emotions, all of which are grouped around a single prototype. This theory makes it easier to understand people's reactions to different words and phrases, because they understand the meaning of that word or phrase depending on how close or far it is to the prototype of a certain category.

E. Paducheva, a well-known scientist in Russian linguistics, devoted her research to the study of the semantics of time and situation categories in the language. Paducheva's research contributed to a clear and systematic analysis of the ways of expressing situations in language. He put forward the idea that "The category of situation is mainly expressed by means of verbs and their various forms, which means the type or condition of a person or an object at a certain time." Analyzing the ways of

expressing situations in the language, Paducheva showed how the meanings in the language can be clearly and systematically expressed depending on the grammatical forms of the verbs, their meaning and context of use.

In his research, the forms of verbs, the additions that increase or limit their meaning, and contextual factors are often analyzed. In particular, this semantic category has not been the object of special research in Uzbek linguistics.

In Uzbek linguistics, the issue of the expression of case meaning was specially studied by R. Rasulov on the example of case verbs. In the scientist's research work entitled "Meaning structure of verbs of the Uzbek language", case verbs in the Uzbek language were semantically classified and each type was given a separate description.

Verbs of state usually express the internal or external state of the subject. They are used to express a person's physical condition, emotions, mental experiences, or environmental conditions. In addition, as a result of studying the meaning of case verbs into their components, the organization of this semantic field from the following lexical-semantic groups was based on R. Rasulov.

1. Continuous verbs. These verbs express an extended or ongoing state and have the expressions "place", "process" and "quantitative". In English it means "continuous" or "progressive" aspects.
2. Action verbs. Verbs of this type indicate a state resulting from an action. For example, it includes expressions such as "is broken", "is written".
3. Action verbs. Action verbs usually express the completion of a task or action. These verbs usually indicate that something has been done or that a process has begun.
4. Action verbs. These verbs express the specific characteristics or state of a certain action. For example, the English verb "run" expresses speed, and "jump" expresses the act of jumping.
5. Qualifying state verbs. These verbs indicate the ability or competence of a person to do a certain job. In English, such modals as "can", "be able to" can be an example of this category.
6. Figurative verbs. Figurative or metaphorical verbs often express something or a situation in a vague or figurative way. Examples include verbs such as "shine" or "reflect".
7. Biological state verbs. These verbs represent the biological processes of the organism. For example, words such as "grow", "decay" belong to this category.
8. Physiological state verbs. Verbs denoting the physiological state of a person or an animal. For example, verbs such as "sweat" and "bleed" represent physiological processes.
9. Mood verbs. These verbs express a person's mental state or feelings. Verbs such as "love", "hate", "enjoy" are aimed at expressing human inner feelings.

In Rasulov's research, semantic features were used as the basis for analyzing the meaning structure of case verbs. Through these features, it shows how verbs of state reflect different states of the subject, what meanings are important in them, and demonstrate the expressive possibilities of the language.

As a result of the analysis of the meaning structure of verbs in the research, it was determined more precisely how Uzbek verbs are divided into different semantic categories, in what contexts and for what purposes they are used. This allows language learners to better understand the rich expressive power of the language and serves as an auxiliary material in language teaching.

In the process of analyzing the meaning structure of mental state verbs, several important structural and semantic parts are usually identified. These components, that is, semantic parts, are the main components that make up the meaning of the verb. For example, the verb "to worry" is one of the

verbs that express a mental state. If the meaning structure of this verb is analyzed, the following components can be identified: 1. Subjective experience: the verb "to worry" reflects the subject's internal experience, that is, the feeling of anxiety or worry. This feeling is usually associated with thoughts of an uncertain or negative future. 2. Logical object: Most often, this is the verb in the sense that the subject refers to the cause of concern about something or someone. For example, in the sentence "She worries about her exams", "her exams" is the logical object of worry. 3. Continuity: The verb "to worry" usually expresses a process that lasts for a certain period of time, rather than a moment. In the sense of this verb, there is an extended state, not a temporary one. 4. Intensity of force: In the meaning of this verb, the strength or intensity of the feeling is also shown. The verb "to worry" can express a relatively low or moderate level of worry, but sometimes it can also express very strong worry or anxiety. 5. Positive or negative meaning: the verb "to worry" mainly has a negative meaning, because the feelings expressed by this verb are often unpleasant and unwanted feelings.

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